

**Ocean Cryosphere Exchanges in Antarctica:
Impacts on Climate and the Earth system**

Greenland ice sheet freshwater implementation in NorESM

Deliverable D5.8

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Lead beneficiary and author:

PP2: Norwegian Research Centre (NORCE): David Chandler

Contributors:

PP2: Norwegian Research Centre (NORCE): Petra Langebroek

Review:

PP1: Danish Meteorological Institute (DMI), Chiara Bearzotti (chb@dmi.dk)

PP6: ETT S.p.A. (ETT): Mariaclaudia Paolini

Cover sheet: Melt water entering a moulin in the Greenland Ice Sheet (photo D. Chandler).

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1. Publishable summary

Earth system models are used for a wide variety of experiments aimed at understanding how different components (atmosphere, ocean, land, ice sheets, etc) interact with each other. These interactions can be studied under past, present and future climates. In particular, Earth system models forced by a range of plausible socioeconomic scenarios in the coming century form the basis of future climate projections within the Climate Model Intercomparison Project (CMIP). There are many potentially important feedbacks between model components, depending on time scales and climate state. One such feedback is between ice sheets and climate: the climate influences the magnitude and distribution of freshwater fluxes discharged from ice sheets, while these freshwater fluxes in turn enter the ocean and influence ocean circulation and climate. Past studies have found both positive (self-amplifying) and negative (self-limiting) feedbacks related to ice sheet freshwater fluxes. Although Earth system models could be the ideal tool for quantifying these climate-ice sheet feedbacks, technical difficulties in the computational implementation of interactions (coupling) between an ice sheet and the rest of the Earth system have necessitated some important compromises in how ice sheets are represented. Detailed knowledge of this implementation is thus needed before designing related experiments.

This deliverable describes how the Greenland Ice Sheet and its associated freshwater fluxes are represented within two versions of the Norwegian Earth System Model (NorESM2). In one version, both the Greenland and Antarctic ice sheets are represented in the simplest way possible (effectively, as snow-covered mountains). This is the version used for the NorESM2 contribution to the latest CMIP phase (CMIP6). In the second version, the Greenland Ice Sheet is represented by a three-dimensional ice flow model that interacts with other model components, while the Antarctic Ice Sheet remains as a snow-covered mountain. This version is currently under development and is likely to participate in the upcoming CMIP7. We finally provide some examples of potentially important differences between the NorESM2 Greenland Ice Sheet and a real ice sheet.

2. Work performed and main achievements

2.1 Description of the work performed

The vast majority of ice loss from the Earth's ice sheets occurs via solid or liquid freshwater fluxes, with the remainder being evaporation or sublimation from the surface. Solid and liquid freshwater fluxes from ice sheets are associated with four processes: (1) runoff of surface melt, from both floating and grounded ice; (2) runoff of basal melting of grounded ice; (3) calving of icebergs from floating ice shelves or marine-terminating glaciers; and (4) ocean-driven melting beneath floating ice shelves and calving fronts. Under our present-day climate, mass loss from the Greenland Ice Sheet is dominated by surface melt runoff and calving, whereas mass loss from Antarctica is dominated by ice shelf basal melt and calving. The way that these fluxes are modelled within NorESM depends on how the Greenland Ice Sheet is included (i.e., interactive/coupled or non-interactive), and this in turn impacts the design and interpretation of freshwater-related experiments, as we will outline in this Section 2. To be clear, an "interactive" or "coupled" ice sheet is included as a discrete component of the Earth system model, where it accepts mass inputs (e.g. snowfall), redistributes mass via ice flow, exports mass (e.g. by melting and iceberg calving), and can evolve its extent and thickness. A "non-interactive" ice sheet is not included as a discrete component, has no representation of ice flow, and maintains constant extent and thickness.

We firstly describe the standard configuration without any interactive ice sheets, which is the configuration used for NorESM2's contribution to CMIP6 (see Seland et al. 2020 and Fig. 2; Section 2.1.1). We then describe how freshwater fluxes are handled in NorESM2 with an interactive Greenland Ice Sheet, but still a

non-interactive Antarctic Ice Sheet (Section 2.1.2); this is a configuration that has been under development since CMIP6 (Goelzer et al., in rev.) and will likely be used in CMIP7.

2.1.1 Ice sheet freshwater fluxes in NorESM2 without interactive ice sheets

In the latest phase of the Climate Model Intercomparison Project (CMIP6), the contributing Earth system models, such as NorESM, did not have interactive ice sheets. Non-interactive ice sheets were instead represented in the land component as snow-covered mountains with fixed topography (Fig. 1). In this representation, floating ice shelves lack an ocean cavity, so the snow-covered mountain and land model extend to the ice shelf front, and the ocean model does not extend beneath the ice shelf.

Fig. 1: Comparison between interactive and non-interactive ice sheets in Earth system models (modified from Swart et al. 2023).

Fig 2: Schematic of NorESM2 without (left) and with (right) a coupled Greenland ice sheet. CISM and the components in blue are common to both NorESM2 and its parent model, the Community Earth System Model (CESM). All interactions between components are implemented via the coupler (CIME), which is not shown here. Modified from Goelzer et al. (in rev.).

The ice sheet surface mass balance (SMB) is calculated in the land model (Community Land Model, CLM5: Fig. 2, 3). Ice sheet grid cells are assigned to the ‘glacier’ land type in CLM5, and SMB is calculated separately for ten discrete elevation bands (‘elevation classes’) within that cell. The grid cell average SMB is

then a weighted mean of the SMBs for each elevation class, with weights equal to the fractional area covered by each class. This approach allows downscaling of coarse-resolution atmosphere forcing from CAM, and is particularly useful in grid cells with a wide range of surface elevations, for example around the margins of the Greenland Ice Sheet.

The snowpack on top of the ice is modelled as discrete layers, and a snow hydrology scheme tracks the bulk properties (e.g., density, liquid water content) of each layer. Surface melt can percolate downwards through these layers, and any liquid water leaving the bottom layer is passed to the coupler as liquid (surface) runoff. For a non-interactive ice sheet, the ice surface topography remains fixed. Since there is no horizontal ice transport, excess snow accumulation must be removed, and any ice melt must be replaced. This is addressed by imposing a maximum snow depth (in NorESM2, this maximum is 10 m snow water equivalent). If the snowpack exceeds this thickness, a corresponding amount of snow is removed from the bottom layer and passed to the coupler. This is known as the ‘snow-capping’ scheme (Fig. 3). Similarly, in ice sheet grid cells where melting leads to net ice loss, a negative solid ice flux is sent to the coupler to replace the ice required to maintain a constant surface elevation.

As an example: suppose an ice sheet in equilibrium is receiving $1M$ Gt/yr of accumulation in the interior (where the snowpack is already at its full capacity), which in reality flows towards the margin and is lost as $0.4M$ Gt/yr surface melt and $0.6M$ Gt/yr calving. In the modelled ice sheet, excess snow in the interior is exported immediately as a solid ice flux instead of flowing outwards to replace melted/calved ice around the margins. Under the snow-capping scheme just described, we would send $1M$ Gt/yr to the coupler as snow-capped solid ice flux, as well as the additional $0.4M$ Gt/yr surface melt exported as liquid runoff, giving a total of $1.4M$ Gt/yr ice loss. However, adjusting the solid ice flux to replace melted ice around the margins reduces the snow-capped solid ice flux by 1 unit for each 1 unit of exported surface melt. Hence, in this example:

Liquid water flux to coupler $q_l = 0.4M$ Gt/yr

Solid ice flux to coupler $q_s = 1M - 0.4M = 0.6M$ Gt/yr

This regains the 0.4:0.6 partitioning between melt and calving.

In NorESM2 these ice sheet related freshwater fluxes are accumulated and passed to the coupler once per month.

Fig. 3: Schematic of how ice sheet freshwater fluxes are created in the land model of NorESM2 without interactive ice sheets.

All runoff from the land model - whether generated by glacier land units or elsewhere - is passed via the coupler to the runoff model (Model for Scale Adaptive River Transport: MOSART, Li et al. 2013) (Fig. 4). Runoff from non-glacier land units is simulated as overland flow in rivers. However, both liquid and solid freshwater fluxes from glacier land units are sent directly from their source grid cell to the nearest coast. In the coupler, ice sheet and river runoff freshwater fluxes are combined and mapped to the corresponding coastal grid cell in the ocean model. However, instead of adding all of the freshwater flux from a coastal land unit grid cell directly into one ocean model grid cell, the coupler spreads out the runoff laterally across an ocean region of a few hundred km in radius (Fig. 5). This avoids numerical instabilities that might arise from adding a lot of freshwater to one ocean model grid cell. A similar remapping step removes heat from a corresponding region of the ocean surface, which is sufficient to melt the solid ice flux.

The ocean model in NorESM (BLOM) conserves water volume, and therefore cannot directly accept a freshwater flux, whether from precipitation, evaporation or runoff. Instead, BLOM adds all the surface freshwater fluxes together, then converts the total to a virtual salt flux.

The final step relevant to the treatment of ice sheet freshwater fluxes is to balance the ocean salinity budget. This is done at each coupling time step by integrating the global virtual salinity flux, and making a small, spatially-uniform adjustment so that it is zero overall.

In summary, freshwater fluxes generated by a non-interactive ice sheet are effectively passed directly from their source grid cell to a region of closest ocean, without any direct impact on either the land or runoff models through which they are transferred. Hence, their only *direct* impacts are confined to the ocean model, such that any impacts on the atmosphere, land and river runoff would have to occur *indirectly* as a result of changes in ocean circulation or surface properties.

Fig. 4: Schematic of how ice sheet freshwater fluxes are passed from the land model to the ocean model, in NorESM2 configurations both with and without interactive ice sheets.

Fig. 5: Example NorESM2 output showing how freshwater fluxes are passed to the ocean model. These plots are annual means for the period 1950-2014 in the CMIP6 historical experiment, with a coupled Greenland Ice Sheet (Table 1 below) and a non-interactive Antarctic Ice Sheet. In the top plot, surface melt from ice sheets and river runoff from the other land surfaces are evident as liquid water fluxes spread across coastal grid cells. In the bottom plot, solid ice fluxes around Greenland come from calving in the ice sheet model or snow-capping of non-ice-sheet grid cells in the land model, while solid ice fluxes around Antarctica come only from snow-capping in the land model. At the tip of the Antarctic Peninsula, there is a small region with negative solid ice flux: this is because surface melting exceeds snow accumulation over the northern part of the peninsula, so a solid ice flux is removed from the ocean to replace net ice loss and maintain the fixed ice sheet topography as explained in Section 2.1.1.

Some potential implications of the treatment of freshwater fluxes from non-interactive ice sheets are summarised below.

- Consider the case that the Greenland Ice Sheet is in equilibrium with the climate. For the real ice sheet (subscript R in the following notation), net snow accumulation in the interior of the ice sheet ($M_{acc,R}$) is balanced by mass loss from net surface melting ($M_{sm,R}$) in the ablation zone and by iceberg calving ($M_{calv,R}$), i.e., $M_{acc,R} = M_{sm,R} + M_{calv,R}$ if we ignore other smaller terms in the mass balance. Correspondingly, the total liquid freshwater received by the ocean is $Q_{liq,R} = M_{sm,R}$, and the total solid discharge received by the ocean is $Q_{ice,R} = M_{calv,R} = M_{acc,R} - M_{sm,R}$. In NorESM2 (subscript N in our

notation), suppose we simulate accumulation and melting reasonably well as $M_{acc,N} \approx M_{acc,R}$ and $M_{sm,N} \approx M_{sm,R}$; in which case we must have $M_{calv,N} \approx M_{calv,R}$. Both the magnitudes and partitioning between solid and liquid fresh water fluxes into coastal waters should therefore be reasonable *in this equilibrium scenario and disregarding decadal-scale variability*, providing accumulation and surface melt are simulated accurately. Unfortunately, the Greenland Ice Sheet is not currently in equilibrium, nor would it be in typical applications of NorESM2 exploring Earth system response to centennial-scale climate warming or other forcing scenarios.

- Suppose NorESM simulates an increase in accumulation ($M_{acc,N}$) over the interior of the ice sheet, whether due to decadal variability or a secular trend. The snow-capping scheme will generate an immediate increase in the solid ice discharge $Q_{ice,N}$ into the ocean (assuming the snowpack is already at 10 m water equivalent). In contrast, an increase in accumulation in the interior of a real ice sheet would be advected towards the margins as an ice thickness anomaly over time scales of centuries to millennia. Consequently, any changes in accumulation ($M_{acc,R}$) would in reality be manifested as a change in ice volume that only impacts freshwater fluxes after a lag of order 100 to 1000 years.
- Suppose NorESM simulates an increase in surface melt ($M_{sm,N}$) around the western margins of the ice sheet. Although the model will correctly increase the liquid water runoff into the ocean, it will remove a solid ice flux from the ocean to replace the surface melt, which of course does not occur in reality (the real ice sheet would become thinner). Hence, $Q_{liq,N}$ would be increased as it should, but $Q_{ice,N}$ would be erroneously decreased by an amount equivalent to the increase in $M_{sm,N}$.

In summary, to study climate periods when the ice sheet is not in equilibrium with the climate forcing, the feedbacks between the ice sheets and the other Earth System components (ocean, land, atmosphere, rivers) should be taken into account by implementing dynamic interactive ice sheets.

2.1.2 Ice sheet freshwater fluxes in NorESM2 with an interactive Greenland Ice Sheet

In the NorESM2 version with an interactive Greenland Ice Sheet, the land model CLM5 is still used to calculate SMB over the ice sheet, and again employing the same downscaling to discrete elevation classes. However, excess snow removed in the snow-capping scheme is sent to the CISM ice sheet model as ice accumulation, instead of being discharged directly to the ocean. There is also no runoff adjustment step, since ice lost as surface melt does not need to be replaced directly. Instead, the ice sheet surface elevation evolves freely depending on the balance of ice accumulation, melt and ice flow.

There is currently no glacial hydrology component in the NorESM2 CISM configuration. Liquid runoff from the land model (drainage from the bottom of the snowpack, plus the liquid fraction of capped snow), is still sent directly to the nearest ocean grid cell, via MOSART. Additional runoff is generated as basal melting of grounded ice, either from geothermal heating or from frictional heat dissipation. This small additional freshwater flux is sent to the coupler and added to the surface melt.

In the NorESM2 CISM configuration, all floating ice is calved immediately, and sent as solid ice flux to MOSART. This is not necessarily a bad assumption in Greenland as floating ice shelves are generally very small (often absent altogether) at marine-terminating outlet glaciers. In this configuration, calving into the ocean is dependent only on the modelled ice flow, and not on ocean conditions, so the coupling is only one-way (ice to ocean) as indicated by the crossed out arrow in Fig 2. One potentially important feedback is missed in this approach: calving rates at the terminus of grounded marine-terminating glaciers are influenced by ocean-driven frontal melting of the submerged portion of the calving front. This frontal melting is in turn dependent on ocean temperature. Including this feedback would require a careful representation of the complexities of heat transfer along the long fjords separating calving fronts from the open ocean, since these fjords are far too narrow to be resolved in the ocean model.

Calved ice is sent from CISM to the runoff model (MOSART), from where it is handled in the same way as snow-capped ice in the non-interactive case.

BLOM requires a constant ocean volume. Therefore, the salinity flux adjustment is still applied when the Greenland Ice Sheet is interactive, even though changes in the ice sheet ice volume will lead to changes in ocean volume and mean salinity. These changes are of course very small in comparison to the total ocean volume, even though their impact on regional sea level rise will potentially have significant socioeconomic consequences under warmer than present climates.

In summary, the main differences between the interactive and non-interactive Greenland Ice Sheet NorESM2 configurations are:

- (1) The solid ice fraction of snow-capped ice is sent to the ice sheet model, where it flows slowly to the ocean instead of being sent directly.
- (2) A negative solid ice flux is not used to replace ice melt.
- (3) Ice sheet topography is not fixed.

Fig. 6: Schematic of how freshwater fluxes are handled in CLM5 and CISM, when an interactive Greenland Ice Sheet is included. Subsequent treatment in MOSART and BLOM is identical to the non-interactive case (Fig 4).

2.2 References

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2.3 Open Science

This deliverable provides a description of the Greenland Ice Sheet freshwater implementation in NorESM, both in a version without dynamic interactive ice sheet, and in the version with interactive Greenland Ice Sheet. The latter version will be used for further Ocean Ice work and the related upcoming D5.9 NorESM2 source code without an interactive Greenland Ice Sheet (as used for CMIP6) can be downloaded here:

<https://github.com/NorESMhub/NorESM/archive/refs/tags/release-noresm2.0.0.zip>

Source code for NorESM2 with a coupled Greenland Ice Sheet, as used by Goelzer et al. (in rev), can be found here:

https://github.com/hgoelzer/NorESM-HGfork/releases/tag/noresm_ism_betzy_mask.

3. Results

This deliverable focused largely on gaining knowledge about how the NorESM2 freshwater fluxes are generated and passed between components. Some specific outcomes are as follows.

- The ice sheet modelling group at NORCE has gained new knowledge of how freshwater fluxes are handled in NorESM2. This knowledge is directing our subsequent OCEAN ICE simulations and helping further development towards a NorESM3 that will participate in the forthcoming CMIP7.
- We have gained a deeper understanding of the scientific limitations imposed by running simulations with a non-interactive ice sheet, for example due to missing feedbacks or a simplified representation of how mass is transferred from an ice sheet accumulation zone to the ocean. These are important limitations to consider when planning simulations and when analysing or interpreting results.
- We have gained a deeper understanding of additional technical challenges when implementing an interactive ice sheet, which leads to some new limitations while mitigating some (but not all) of the limitations associated with a non-interactive ice sheet.

4. Impact

This deliverable contributes to achieving the project's following objectives, as described in the description of the action.

O5: Assess how global ocean circulation is impacted by freshwater discharge from the northern and southern ice sheets.

This deliverable contributes to this specific objective by providing a thorough analysis of the computation of glacial freshwater discharge and how this is implemented in a typical Earth System Model (NorESM2), both in a case without interactive ice sheets (CMIP6 models) and in the case of an interactive Greenland Ice Sheet and a non-interactive Antarctic Ice Sheet. The specifics of these calculations and feedbacks, will ensure a proper implementation of freshwater “hosing” simulations with NorESM in the next step, where we focus on northern and southern sourced freshwater forcing on global ocean circulation.

O7: Deliver free and open access to all data obtained in the project and contribute to international assessments (e.g. IPCC), climate model development, multi-national ocean observing initiatives (e.g. SOOS, All-Atlantic Ocean Research Alliance) and policymakers.

Our new knowledge of how ice sheet freshwater fluxes are handled in NorESM2 will form a basis for designing subsequent NorESM2 simulations in our ongoing OCEAN ICE work (due to be reported in D5.9). Since we also collaborate with colleagues on the NorESM development team, our discussions of freshwater fluxes with these colleagues help shape how ice sheets and their feedback will be implemented in future NorESM developments.